

Diagnostic Accuracy of MDCT Scan in Detection of Intestinal and Mesenteric Injury in Blunt Abdominal TraumaSangada Santosh Surmalbhai¹, Majmudar Drusty Krishnasevak², Darda Mihir Gautam³, Vaidya Chirayu Vijaykumar⁴¹Second Year Resident, Department of Radio diagnosis, NHL Medical College Shardaben Hospital, Saraspur, Ahmedabad-380018, Gujarat, India²Associate Professor, Department of Radio diagnosis, NHL Medical College Shardaben Hospital, Saraspur, Ahmedabad-380018, Gujarat, India³Senior Resident, Department of Radio diagnosis, NHL Medical College Shardaben Hospital, Saraspur, Ahmedabad-380018, Gujarat, India⁴Associate Professor, Department of Medicine, Nootan Medical College & Research Center, Visnagar, Pin- 384315, Gujarat, India

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Abstract:**Background:** Abdominal trauma caused by blunt force is a common presentation in the emergency room. The chief causes of blunt abdominal trauma are motor vehicle accidents, falls from heights, assault, bicycle injuries, injuries sustained during sporting activities, and industrial accidents. There are several recognized signs of blunt bowel and mesenteric injury at multidetector CT. Familiarity with the appearance of the signs as well as the limitations is crucial to making a timely diagnosis.**Results:** Most patients were males (77.21%) & most common age group was 21-40 years (73%). Most common mode of injury was road traffic accidents (70%). Ileum (35%) was the most common site of injury followed by jejunum (25%). Most common CT scan findings were mesenteric stranding (73%) followed by free fluid (80%) 93%. The most common solid organ injured was the spleen followed by the liver. The skeletal injury was the most common extra-abdominal injury.**Conclusion:** Males were more commonly injured most common mode of injury is road traffic/motor vehicle accidents. Most common site of injury is ileum. Most common associated solid organ injury is spleen. Most frequent MDCT findings are mesenteric stranding, free fluid and bowel wall thickening. Most specific findings are bowel wall discontinuity, active extravasation and reduced bowel wall enhancement.**Keyword:** MDCT Scan, Accidents, Blunt Abdominal Trauma, Contrast Extravasation.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Blunt abdominal trauma is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality among all age groups. Blunt abdominal trauma usually results from motor vehicle collisions, recreational accidents, or falls. Men tend to be affected slightly more often than women. The most commonly injured organs are the spleen, liver, retro peritoneum, small bowel, kidneys, bladder, colorectal, diaphragm, and pancreas.

Blunt bowel and mesenteric injuries (BBMI) are rare injuries with high morbidity and mortality, and occur in only 1-5% of blunt abdominal traumas [1-4]. Accurate diagnosis is of great importance since delayed diagnosis of BBMI may result in serious complications and mortality. Early diagnosis of isolated BBMI is difficult in patients with blunt abdominal trauma as clinically apparent signs and

symptoms of peritonitis caused by perforation can be observed only after a considerable period of time, causing delayed diagnosis. As a result of delay in diagnosis, intraabdominal complications, such as abscess, sepsis, and even mortality, can be seen after surgical repair. [5-7]

Signs and symptoms of peritonitis like rigidity, tenderness, and rebound are sometimes undetectable and abdominal examination findings may be obscure in patients critically injured or neurologically compromised or in those experiencing an altered sensorium resulting from drugs, alcohol intoxication, or central nervous system trauma simultaneously. Currently, the diagnostic modalities besides physical examinations are paracentesis, diagnostic peritoneal lavage, focused abdominal sonogram for

trauma, computed tomography (CT) scan, and laparoscopy. [7-15] Multidetector computed tomography (MDCT) is an excellent imaging modality for diagnosing and managing patients with abdominal injuries while playing critical role in describing and grading solid-organ injuries, diagnosing the significance of BBMI, and deciding whether surgical intervention is required. MDCT readily detects direct and indirect features of bowel and/or mesenteric injury which is an important advance given that unrecognized bowel and mesenteric injuries may result in high morbidity and mortality.

Multidetector computed tomography (MDCT) offers significantly faster scanning times and improved image resolution due to thinner collimation and reduced partial volume and motion artifacts. The ability of CT to perform and produce fast-processing images, such as multiplanar reconstruction (MPR), is important for accurate interpretation of abnormalities.

If patients are hemodynamically unstable, detection of suspected bowel and mesenteric injuries is necessary for emergency surgical treatment. However, if patients are hemodynamically stable and no suspicious BBMI is present on MDCT, nonsurgical management is the acceptable standard care for blunt abdominal trauma.

Materials and Methods:

Study Design: This is a hospital based prospective study done of patients with blunt abdominal injury who underwent CT scan evaluation of abdomen and pelvis in the Department of radiodiagnosis, after obtaining approval from the institutional ethics committee. The study period was from September 2022 to October 2023.

In this study 30 cases of blunt abdominal trauma with bowel and mesenteric injury are selected. In all these cases haemodynamic stabilization was done if required before being referred for CT scan. All patients underwent x-ray and ultrasound examinations prior to CT scan evaluation. Individual details, clinical history and any significant past history was recorded. Also relevant laboratory investigations were done. Follow up with surgical department was done to compare our findings.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. CT scan is performed in hemodynamically stable blunt abdominal injury cases in whom findings on clinical abdominal examination or sonologic findings are equivocal,
2. In whom important signs such as guarding/rigidity could not be adequately evaluated due to altered mental status.
3. Patients in whom ultrasound shows free fluid and further evaluation for bowel injury is sought by clinician.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Hemodynamically unstable patients
2. Patients with obvious clinical signs who require immediate surgery.
3. Isolated solid organ injury.
4. Consent not given.

MDCT Technique: All studies were obtained on a Philips MX 16-slice MDCT with collimation 16x1.5mm, pitch 0.8632, tilt zero, rotation time 0.75 seconds and 300 FOV. Area of examination was taken from the diaphragm to pubic symphysis with 200 mAs and 120 kVp. Patients were supine. A multiphase 16-slice MDCT scan, including plain, arterial, portal and venous phases, was conducted by the same technique at 5 mm slice thickness, and reconstructed in the axial, coronal, and sagittal planes at 0.625 mm section thickness.

Pre intravenous contrast administration scans were obtained without oral & rectal contrast. Thereafter, an intravenous contrast agent (Iohexol) containing 300 mg/ml iodine was administered in a dose of 1 mL/kg, saline infusion 25-30 ml at a rate of 3 mL/s using a power injector. The arterial and portal phases were initiated at 25–30s and 60–70s delay, respectively. An excretory phase (3–5 min) was performed in case blunt renal-collecting-system injury was suspected.

Results:

Twenty-five of 30 patients in present study underwent surgery. Five patients were conservatively treated. Twenty of 25 patients had surgically proven BBMI and 5 patients had no BBMI. Of the twenty patients with BBMI, 15 (75%) had bowel injury, 2 (10%) had mesenteric injury, and 3 (15%) had bowel and mesenteric injury.

Table 1: Sex Wise Distribution Pattern (N=30)

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	23	77
Female	7	23

Table 2: Age Wise Distribution Pattern (N=30)

Age	No. of Patients	Percentage (%)
11-20yr	1	4
21-30yr	13	43
31-40yr	9	30
41-50yr	4	14
51-60yr	3	9

Our results showed that male patients were overwhelming with a rate of 77.21% & most common age group was 21-40 years (73%).

Table 3: Mode of Injury wise Distribution Pattern

Mode of injury	No. of patients	Percentage (%)
Traffic accident	21	70
Abuse/Work-relatedaccident	6	20
Other	3	10

The majority of the patients (70%) in our study sustained injuries due to road traffic accidents.

Table 4: Site of Injury Wise Distribution (N=20)

Site of Injury	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Stomach	1	05
Duodenum	2	10
Jejunum	5	25
Ileum	7	35
Cecum	1	05
Appendix	0	0
Colon	2	10
Mesentery	5	25

In this study, ileum (35%) was the most common site to get injured followed by jejunum (25%).

Table 5: Distributions Based On Ct Findings (N=30)

MDCT findings	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Bowel wall discontinuity	4	13
Active extravasation	2	6
Free fluid	24	80
Bowel wall thickening	18	60
Reduced bowel-wallenhancement	7	23
Pneumoperitoneum	14	46
Mesenteric hematoma	5	16
Mesenteric stranding	22	73

In our study the most frequently suspected injuries based on CT scan were mesenteric stranding (73%) followed by free fluid(80%) and bowel wall thickening(60%). Bowel wall discontinuity was reported in 13% of the cases in our study.

Figure 1: Case 2- 32 yr old patient with blunt trauma. CT findings are mesenteric haematoma, mesenteric stranding and free fluid with liver contusions andrib fractures

Figure 2: Case 1 - 25 yr old patient with RTA. CT findings showing active contrast extravasation, free fluid, mesenteric stranding and splenic contusion

Figure 3: Case 19 - 25 yr old patient with RTA. CT images show transverse colon-bowel wall defect, pneumoperitoneum, free fluid and splenic contusions

Table 6: Statistics of MDCT Findings

	Bowel-Wall Discontinuity	Active Extravasation	Free Fluid	Bowel-Wall Thickening	Reduced Bowel-Wall Enhancement	Pneumoperitoneum	Mesenteric Hematoma	Mesenteric Stranding
True positive	4	2	17	11	7	13	4	15
True Negative	5	20	1	3	5	6	4	2
False positive	0	0	4	4	0	1	1	3
False negative	16	3	3	7	13	5	16	5
Sensitivity	20	40	85	61	35	85	20	75
Specificity	100	100	20	42	100	72	80	40
Positive predictive value	100	100	80	73	100	92	80	83
Negative predictive value	23	86	50	30	27	54	20	28

Bowel-wall discontinuity was considered as a direct finding of blunt bowel injury, and active extravasation suggested that an active bleeding condition has high specificity of 100% and 100% and low sensitivity of 20% and 40%, respectively. In our study, Pneumoperitoneum had a sensitivity and specificity of 85% and 72%, respectively.

Table 7: Associated Abdominal Injuries (N=30)

Organ	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Spleen	10	33
Liver	7	23
Kidney	4	13
Pancreas	3	10
Urinary Bladder	2	6
Other organs	4	13

Table 8: Categorizations on Extra-Abdominal Injury

Type of injury	Frequency	Percentage (%)
skeletal system	7	23
Blunt trauma chest	5	16
Head injury	1	0.03
Other	1	0.03

In our study, 93% patients had associated intra-abdominal injuries and 46 % patients had extra-abdominal injuries. The most common solid organ injured was the spleen followed by the liver. The skeletal injury was the most common extra-abdominal injury followed by a blunt chest trauma.

Discussion

Our results showed that male patients were overwhelming with a rate of 77.21%. Similar rates were reported by Duy Hung N et al [16] with 87.21 % and Elton et al. [17] 70.4%. Blunt bowel and mesenteric injuries are often present and can be misdiagnosed in multiple simultaneous accidents [18]

The most common age group in the present study was 21-40 years (73%). Wadhwa M et al [19] and Ayoade et al. [20] also found this age group to have the highest incidence in their study 54% & 68.9% respectively. This might be for the reason that this age group forms a major segment of the workforce. The majority of the patients in our study as well as other studies sustained injuries due to road traffic accidents. In Duy Hung N et al [16] it was (79.1%), In Polat AV et al [21] (88%) & In Elton et al [17] (63%).

In this study, ileum was the most common site to get injured followed by jejunum which was the same as reported by Polat AV et al [21] with Ileum (50%), Duy Hung N et al [16] and Wadhwa M [19] et al reported jejunum (41%) & (50%) respectively followed by ileum as the most common site. Small bowel injuries mainly happen within proximity to the duodenojejunal flexure and ileocecal junction, i.e., close to fixed points, and a majority of them are located on the anti-mesenteric border. Large bowel injuries generally occur in penetrating trauma, whereas in blunt trauma, it is a less common find-

ing. In our study, the large bowel was injured less frequently in comparison to small bowel injury. This has also been reported in various other studies that colonic injuries occurred less frequently than small bowel injuries [22]. This is mainly due to its location and the lack of redundancy, which prevents the formation of closed loops. [22-23]

In our study the most frequently suspected injuries based on CT scan were mesenteric stranding followed by free fluid and bowel wall thickening. Studies by T. Be'ge et al [24] and Polat AV et al [21] also suggest similar findings. Bowel wall discontinuity was reported in 13% of the cases in our study. In a study by Brofman et al. [25], 7 % cases were reported. They postulated that the relative infrequency of observations of this feature is likely due to small size of the discontinuities, which are evident at surgery only with careful inspection.

Bowel-wall discontinuity was considered as a direct finding of blunt bowel injury, and active extravasation suggested that an active bleeding condition has high specificity of 100% and 100% and low sensitivity of 20% and 40%, respectively. Our result was comparable to those reported by Polat AV et al [21], Duy Hung N et al [16] and Hiba Abdel-Aziz et al [26] which confirmed that these characteristics are not highly sensitive. Since bowel-wall rupture frequently occurs at the antimesenteric side of bowel loops, it could be misdiagnosed on a MDCT scan if its size is small. [27] Similarly, a small vessel tear could be occulted by mesenteric hematoma. Nonetheless, a finding of active extravasation should be taken into consideration as an indication for simultaneous surgery [5-25]. Reduced bowel-wall enhancement may represent an ischemic bowel due to the rupture of supplied arteries or arterial occlusions. [17] In our study, this feature had a sensitivity of 35%, which was lower than that reported

by Polat AV et al [21], and higher than the result reported by Duy Hung N et al; [16] it also had specificity of 100%, which was in line with findings that reported by these authors.

Pneumoperitoneum was, according to previous studies, a highly specific indication for intestinal perforation but it could contribute to a false-positive diagnosis of bowel perforation [21,25,28] In our study, this finding had a sensitivity and specificity of 85% and 72%, respectively. Our result was comparable to those reported by Duy Hung N et al. [16] Polat AV et al [21] and Hiba Abdel-Aziz et al [26] reported low sensitivity and high specificity. Free intraperitoneal air can also be induced by pneumothorax, diaphragm disruption or mechanical ventilation. [23] Bowel-wall thickening, mesenteric hematoma, mesenteric stranding, and free fluid are indirect findings of blunt bowel and mesenteric injuries. The sensitivity and specificity of these findings were differently described in previous studies. Mirvis et al. [30] stated that free fluid and bowel-wall thickening were unspecific findings that might be present in cases of hypovolemic shock in the setting of the trauma, particularly associated with liver or splenic injuries [30]. Our study showed that free fluid and mesenteric stranding are sensitive but less specific findings. Mesenteric hematoma was more specific and less sensitive finding. Bowel wall thickening was more sensitive and less specific finding.

Abdominal trauma is commonly associated with other injuries that complicate the management and also affect the outcome. [31] In our study, 93% patients had associated intra-abdominal injuries and 46 % patients had extra-abdominal injuries. The most common solid organ injured was the spleen followed by the liver. In Duy Hung N et al [16] and Wadhwa M et al [19] also showed similar results. The skeletal injury was the most common extra-abdominal injury followed by a blunt chest trauma. Ayoade et al. [20] and Wadhwa M et al [19] also showed skeletal injuries to be the most common associated extra-abdominal injury.

Conclusion

Males were more commonly injured as compared to females. Most common age group involved is 21-40 years. Most common mode of injury is road traffic/motor vehicle accidents. Most common site of injury is ileum. Most common associated solid organ injury is spleen. Most frequent MDCT scan findings are mesenteric stranding, free fluid and bowel wall thickening. Most specific findings are bowel wall discontinuity, active extravasation and reduced bowel wall enhancement. Hence, multidetector CT scan can be used as the modality of choice in case of patients with suspected intestinal and mesenteric injury in blunt abdominal trauma. Also the indirect signs should be given as much

importance as the direct signs. Bowel-wall thickening, mesenteric stranding, and free fluid are indirect findings of blunt bowel and mesenteric injuries. They are less specific findings. However, showed a higher sensitivity and are more frequently seen.

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